

OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO

Data source: Personal Expertise

By olusegun oladosu, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile - Ife

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Oyo religion, Language, Yoruba

Oyo people are a distinct linguistic group among the Yoruba race. They had one of the strongest military among the Yoruba prior to colonial rule. They held strongly to their traditional religious views which, as they claimed, helped in their successful military campaigns. They are found in present day Oyo state, Nigeria. Their population is about 471,000. From oral history, the town was founded by Oranmiyan the last son of Oduduwa, the great ancestor of the Yoruba people. Generally, the religious and political history of the people can be traced to their migration from Ile-Ife. But more specifically, they have a ritual tradition which is spectacular. It is attached to Sango and Oya festivals. Oya was the wife of Sango during his life time. In cosmological understanding of Orisa belief, she was such an outstanding figure among the female deities. Her imposing pedigree therefore makes her group to be unique. The group showcases her festival with Bata drum as it makes it distinct for ritual practices. This unique ritual practice of the Oya group is shared with the Sango group. Oral tradition has it that Oya was one of the deities sent to the earth by Olodumare for creation and earth-remodelling. She is reputed for her fearlessness and believed to live in or inhabit the wind. Oya is known for her reputable character as a warrior and as a mother that loves children. Oya is a goddess that professes love in her character. This is seen from the way she stood with her husband, Sango, in the time of crisis. She is a mother who protects her children from any form of danger because she accords wealth to them and does not support hypocritical acts and betrayal. Rather, she loves people who are truthful and those who possess a pure heart. A mythical narrative made it clear that Oya was so faithful to Sango, her husband that she alone of all his wives accompanied him in his flight towards Nupeland in his time of crisis. Oya, according to the myth could not bear the pain of her husband's disappearance after his death that she committed suicide. This act was her way of sharing in her husband's destiny. she died in her hometown, Ira and was thus deified. The Oya group has a well developed religious cult on the River Niger in Nigeria to symbolize her heroic acts. The cult is still devoted to their practices till today. While Sango is recognized as the spirit of thunder and lightning, Oya is known to be the spirit of wind. Sango is acknowledged for fierce tornadoes and intense thunderstorm while Oya is reputed for her windstorms which uproot trees and destroy houses. Oya is seen as a deified heroine and never spoken of as dead. Her votaries still belief that she is still living. She is not dead as she is both a deity and an ancestor who protects and watches over her living children or followers. The Indigenous religious festival, Ìṣṣẹ̀ is performed by her group. This has been incorporated into some new religious traditions among some African groups in the Diaspora.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 1900 CE

Region: Oyo

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa, Oyo state

This is a map of Oyo City in Oyo State in Nigeria, West Africa. Most Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria, while Muslims tend to live in northern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ologundudu Dayo ,The Cradle of Yoruba Culture, USA: Centre for Spoken Words, 2008
- Source 2: Samuel Johnson, The History of the Yoruba's, Lagos: CSS,2001
- Source 3: Judith Gleason, Oya in the Company of Saints, Journal of the America Academy of Religion, Vol.68, No.2, 2000

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oriire.com/article/the-mythical-journey-of-oya-an-exploration-of-african-mythology>
- Source 1 Description: This source narrates African mythology with diverse tales, heroes, and deities that shape the cultural fabric of the Yoruba continent. In the narrative, Oya, holds a special place in the lore of Yoruba mythology. This source explores the mythological journey of Oya, analyzing her significance, defining characteristics, and cultural influences. It also investigates her role as a goddess of the wind, storms, and the transformative power of change
- Source 2 URL: <https://en.oshaeifa.com/orisha/oya/>
- Source 2 Description: This source is a revelation of the true figure of Oya. It discusses her personality and status within the pantheon of Yoruba orisas. Her ferocious power that which made her to be spiritually relevant compared to that of Sango is given due consideration in this essay. Her high profile as Sango's wife is seen through this source as a serious element of esoteric and metaphysical features.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.amplifyafrica.org/the-ancient-beliefs-of-african-goddesses/>
- Source 3 Description: This source makes a description of African belief in Supreme God as a reality never to be doubted. It traces the structure of this belief to three major divisions. The division includes primordial, deified and personified entity. The source showcases the place of female deities in the division as the special divine portion assigned to them by Supreme God. Here the place of Osun, Oya and others were relevantly noted.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://yagbeonilu.com/oya-buffalo-woman/>
- Source 1 Description: The site is accessible with over 50 translations of different languages of Oya heritage. The presentation is done in music and language context.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There are meetings of cultural groups where members from different religious groups apart from the target religion always meet with each others.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: It shared cultural contact with sango religious group. They are not competitive because they have almost the same feature of worship.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Religious affiliation of the group can be through initiation, selection by the the deity of the group and through filial generation.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: The position of arugba votary in this group is designed mainly for female.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of arugba votary

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Through divination or divine selection.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Membership recruitment is not a major concern of the group. People who seek spiritual help or solution to life crisis always find their way to the group. Some of them become members of the group when they have found reprieve for their problems.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Indigenous religious practitioners do not have official backing of the government . Their challenges are not given priority in some cases.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 471

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: According to a Yoruba myth , Oya was the favorite wife of Sango. The significance of the Oya festival in Oyo town stems from the historical belief that oya during her time on earth , once resided in oyo town alongside her husband Sango. So ,in this case , an account of Oya cannot be given without mentioning Sango. Sango who was later deified chooses Oya as his beloved wife and Oya identified with Sango in the manner which she died. Oya group is therefore seen as part of Sango larger group.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The religious functionaries referred to as priests and priestesses are essential guardians of the festival's cultural and spiritual legacy. Their responsibilities are diverse, encompassing roles from leading ceremonies to deciphering the will of Oya and nurturing the spiritual growth of the community.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: The religious leadership include Oya as the chief priestess, alase oloya and Oluwo as the next in rank and arugba oya and gbegba aje oloya as the third in rank.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - Yes
- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - Yes
- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - No
- ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The leader may have a divine instruction from the gods to select his or her successor.
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: In selection process, divine instructions are given through divination by consulting the supernatural concerning who will be taken as next leader in cases.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In case of mistakes, other group leaders always make charges for against the affected member.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Any pronouncement must be carefully dissected through divine commands before acceptance.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group lore has always been passed down orally. there is no set of beliefs, no holy book such as the Bible or the Quran. Cultural beliefs and rules for living are passed down from generation to generation by word of mouth.. Members are trained from childhood to perform prodigious acts of memorization, reciting the whole history of the community for successive generations.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The oral sources of their scripture includes proverbs, songs, invocation, mythical narratives, ritual practices and incantation.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Due to Oya's ferocious powers, certain ecology were created and chanted during periods of her veneration.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: Due to its transmission from generation to generation, its content may be altered and render incomplete . If the original custodian is no longer alive then there can be distortion in the content of the oral story.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious

community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: This is done by religious functionaries like priests and priestesses that have supernatural strength and wisdom to evoke spiritual powers. They are people who go through the procedure of ritual initiation rites and therefore considered worthy of performing rituals that sustain links between the physical and the cosmic forces that Oya represents.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The monumental religious architecture linked to this group is found in a city called Ira. Ira is a religious center founded by the son of oya known as Laage . The time when Sango committed suicide by hanging, his wife oya also relocated to this city where his son resides and there she entered and disappeared into the ground. The forest then became the location of the monument set aside for oya worship in ira till today. The adherents usually makes pilgrimage to this location.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 20

Notes: It is village settlement known as IRA. The reason for the sayin Sango wole ni koso, Oya wole ni Ile Ira (sango entered the ground in Koso while Oya entered the ground in Ira)

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 15

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 20

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Oya is identified by her group as IYAASAN(mother of nine). It is noted that nine children used to accompany her in her itinerary. There is an icon that showcase this company.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: spirit of the wind

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The sacred site in Ira is located in the forest. This forest is linked with the ferocious power of oya found in the wind, rain and storm . when there is weather changes and the forest shakes , this is associated with the display of environmental power of oya.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The period of oya festival is known to be the period when all children of Oyo and Ira from far and near make pilgrimage back home to celebrate the event. This has changed as many indigenes of these communities no longer follow Oya religious beliefs.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the spirits of departed human beings remain around their kith and kin after death and can still appear to their family in case there is need for serious warning or help in period of dilemma. So spirit- body distinction among members of the group can be identified.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: esoteric powers are associated with the spirit minded supernatural forces. likewise the ancestors.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: These are the categories of nature spirits and ancestral spirits

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The ancestral spirits are spirits of the dead . Their habitat is essentially local and they hover around where their living successors dwell.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The belief of this group concerning afterlife is world affirming not renouncing. They have a strong desire on the part of the living to have their parents reincarnated as soon as possible after their death.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The location of afterlife is described in two ways "orun rere' or " orun baba eni" which is good heaven,the second is the heaven of the potsherd " orun apadi".The good heaven is the heaven of the ancestors where relatives who have gone earlier welcome the incoming into their midst. The place is meeting of reunion where they would have everlasting existence.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: There is the realm of ancestors known as the cult of the ancestor where dead can reincarnate into anew life and new beginning .

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: This is the space where those who lived and fulfilled the conditions of being an ancestor gather . this is known as the cult of ancestor

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: This happen when the soul of the departed ancestor return to be born as a grandchild to a child of the departed parents.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: There is a partial reincarnation where the ancestor assumes two distinct identities concurrently. They achieve these by partially appearing as a member of the family and as well still maintaining the identity of the grand or great grand parent. This is an indication that the group considers this world as world affirming where rewards are given to the dead.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The corpses of important elders who held significant positions in the group or community must be given an acceptable ritual ceremony before the body is lowered into the grave.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: shedding of animal bloods are essential for the body of religious leaders and head of the community.

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: sacred materials like cloth and other ritual paraphernalia belonging to the deceased are enclosed

↳ Valuable items:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases bodies of community leaders must be laid according to the custom and specification. The bodies are buried at special locations where ancestors are taken to.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: In this case, Oya the wife of Sango left Oyo for Ira, a town in Kwara after her husband's death. The city was founded by her son Laage. According to history, this city became popular in Yorubaland because it was there that Oya translated to another realm of existence. The group therefore visits the tomb every year.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In the cosmology of the Yoruba, the supernatural beings and ancestors are considered to be ubiquitous. They bear the features of filial piety. Their presence is felt among the human community. The religious groups which identify with this phenomenon claim that they feel the presence of these supernatural beings in their various domains.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: By attributing omniscience to God, the group place him in the highest possible position. In their sight, wisdom commands the greatest respect of everyone. a person who is considered wise in this case is in a special class of his own. Among the group Olodumare is at the top of their religious ranking.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - Yes
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

Notes: The high god (Olodumare) is the supreme authority in their religious tradition. The coordination and control of activities on earth directed by Him. So He has knowledge of this world.

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: He has overall power on people

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god has knowledge of other spiritual entities like deity, spirits and ancestors associated with the human religious activities and sacred practices.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: He forgives the wrongdoings as well reward the good gestures of humankind.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: Sacrifices offered by the group are made to feed the gods/deities who are answerable to the supreme being

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: This act is not known as worship but veneration

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme God can be called upon anywhere and the group believe that where a person may be God can be approached and he in return can communicate to man through several means.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: In olden days human spirits could appear to people but with the influence of civilization the sacredness has changed due to excesses of human misdeeds.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They could be emotional and can feel pain like other human beings.

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: have physical emotion and can feel pain like others

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– No

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: There are primordial, deified and personified model of pantheon

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: There are many times when the living must remember the ancestors that were canonized as deities. If these duties are forgotten, the living-dead become angry and bring trouble to the living.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Worshippers have to uphold taboos that are placed on food as well as observe the right mode of worship. Taboos are placed on what to use or what not to use as sacrifice. It would be a ritual taboo for the children of Oya to raise a dog or come close to animals like sheep, ram or their hair or wool. Oya must not be fed with palm kernel oil, dog and male or female sheep.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Children of Oya should not raise a dog or come close to things like sheep, ram, their hair or wool. Oya must not be fed with palm kernel oil, dog, male or female sheep.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: As a means of social control, there are ways in which relationship involving sex are condoned. There are restrictions guided by taboo.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: There is caution in the way you relate with other members wife

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Generally incest is a taboo among the Yoruba people.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

Notes: Type of marriages like gay, lesbianism and other type like incest or bestiality are not allowed in the group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Some deities and divinities represent the divine wrath of god. They also act as guardians and policemen of public morality. In this wise when certain diseases like smallpox or pestilence are ravaging, the common understanding to this is the wrath of god in display. To avoid disaster and misfortunes like this, man must be in the right spirit with them.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: through golden rule and karmal principle

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Divinities punish those who disobey the norms of the society with sickness and misfortunes and reward with prosperity those who conform to the rules and regulation of the society.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba describes the afterlife in two ways . There is "orun rere" good heaven, the second is "orun buburu" bad heaven. Those who go to good heaven live a happy and comfortable life. The good heaven is the heavens of the ancestors . In afterlife , God will judge according to how one has lived on earth.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Doing good and putting up a reliable character during life time is always the message that the living dead are remembered for. In this way , the living are encouraged to be good because every actions in their life time are rewarded after death. Part of the reward endowed them to be consulted and honored among the family even after death. In the afterlife, they are recognized as part of the ancestors that family trusted.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: There is the claim of partial reincarnation that serve as mean of rewarding the living dead.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The living members of the family who comply or conform to the norms and social order, are rewarded. Ancestors reward such living members with protection, procreation, good health, security from accidents, peace and prosperity.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: There is the belief that human existence will continue forever. The eschatology found among the Yoruba is rigidly enshrined in the concept of their ancestral belief system . This system is seen as the beginning of a new life, a more enhanced life with more vital force in the invisible world of ancestor. This makes provision for the understanding of the concept of reincarnation to be the type that recognize the world in Yoruba cosmology as an affirming one. This is seen in the example of a grandchild that came back to be born to the children of their grand parents .

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are social norms that regulates control of human relationship within groups and the environment. This underline the fact that without the religious activity of man there will be no change in the world.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are norms guiding marriage relationships. Members must honour and respect their members' spouse by not having extra marital affairs with them.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The central virtues is that, you are not allowed to steal peoples property.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes

- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes

- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Sex relationship between male to female is allowed . Sexual relationship in form of marriage between same gender is forbidden as it is seen as taboo among the group.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The female arugba which is the votary of oya must abstain from sex for specific period of time.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The group must not raise a dog or come close to things like sheep or ram

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: There is no self sacrifice among members. The only suicide recorded within the group was the case of the leading goddess(oya) who took her life because of her husband (sango) death following her husband example and also sharing part of her husband destiny (that is, been loyal to her husband through the type of death that claimed her husband life) .

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 4

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Oya festival is important because the festival stand as a frontline for the celebration of sango festival. without the coming out of oya during the festival , sango festival cannot be held. Other devotees in other state also have the privilege of celebrating oya festival at whatever time of the month they want but they give more reference to the celebration of oya festival in oyo town, which stand as the source. The twelfth month of the year is general to all practitioners in all states , at the twelfth month they all celebrate oya for seven days with ritual and thanksgiving.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: There are foods associated with oya and most of these foods are used as a form of worship which includes kola nut, egbo (maize food), akara (bean cake), isapa (native soup), amala (yam flour), lyan (pounded yam), a female chicken, pap, bitter kola, honey and goat. The following must not be taken by oya and her devotees- sheep, dog and buffalo.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: The wool made from the air of sheep must be used by the group

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: This is recognized for distant relations, but relationship on blood is highly emphasized . This is clearly seen in the principle of consanguinity(alajobi concept in Yoruba phenomenon)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: OYO kingdom was once an empire during the ancient period. They still make reference to this anytime.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: There are community association linked with cooperative society in terms of thrift that are given to farmers to improve their production.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Fadama farming scheme is a national farming program that provides opportunity for the group

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: There is local cooperative thrift that give financial benefits to group

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: federal grants are available for group benefits

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are NGO'S that provide health care benefits for the elderly and others in several ways.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are government schools and institutions from primary levels to university for adherent to attend.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There are NGO'S and government bureaucracy that engaged the group and other affiliate of religious societies

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: It is the government that make provision for this through the grassroot government.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government provision are made for people in this regard

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: adults are to pay taxes to the government

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Security outfits belong to the government and no religious group is allowed to float any parallel security outfit.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents are bind by the rules and regulation of the state and country in which the group belong.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The group adopts their local Yoruba language which is the language of communication in their region.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English language is available for the group

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English language is considered as the official language for all citizen.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: There is an informal local calendar which is different from Gregorian calendar used generally in the country.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Gregorian calendar used in several regions of the world is available for the group

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: There are several family famine scheme through which food are provided for the group.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Lugira, Aloysius . World Religions: African Traditional Religions. New York: Chelsea House, 2009.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Salami, Ayo. Yoruba Theology and Tradition: The Genealogy. Lagos: NIDD Publishing Company, 2008.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Olajubu, Oludare. Iwe Asa Bile Yoruba. Lagos: Longman Nigeria, 1978.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Gehman, Richard . African Traditional Religion :in the Light of the Bible. Plateau: Acts, 2013.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Ajibade, Olusola. "Sango's Erindinlogun Divinatory System". In Sango in Africa and the African in Diaspora. Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 2009.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Hallgren, Roland. The Good Things in Life: A Study of the Traditional Religious Culture of the Yoruba People. Loberod: Plus Ultra, 1988.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Ologundudu, Dayo. The Cradle of Yoruba Culture. USA: Center for Spoken Words/ Institute of Yoruba Culture, 2008.

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Gleason, Judith. "Oya in the Company of Saints". Journal of the American Academy of Religion Vol.68, no. 2 (2000).

Reference: OYA RELIGIOUS GROUP IN OYO, Kilson, Marion . "Women in African Traditional Religions". Journal of Religion in Africa Vol.8, no. 5 (1976).